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IDENTIFICATION OF SPECIES OF EMERIA OF TURKEYS USING REGRESSION ANALYSIS OF MORPHOMETRIC INDICATORS OF OCYCYSTS

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The aim. Identify the species of oocysts of turkeys by morphometric parameters.

Material and methods. *Eimeria* oocysts obtained from faeces of suspects and patients with spontaneous eimeriosis of turkeys of poultry farms of Kharkiv region served as material for the research. Methods used: parasitological, coprological, light microscopy, morphometry, mathematical and statistical, correlation and regression analysis, ANOVA variation statistics.

Results. Morphometrically ($n=255$) samples of turkey eimeria oocysts were studied and identified to the species: *E. gallopavonis* ($n=50$), *E. meleagrimitis* ($n=50$), *E. adenoids* ($n=51$), *E. meleagridis* ($n=53$), *E. innocua* ($n=51$) according to identification indicators (X_1 - length of the oocyst in μm ; X_2 - width of the oocyst in μm ; X_3 - area of the oocyst in μm^2 ; X_4 - eccentricity of the model ellipse; X_5 - ratio of the width of the oocyst to its length; X_6 - largest curvature and X_7 - smallest curvature in its model ellipse poles on the major and minor axes, respectively, in μm , X_8 - presence - 1 or absence - 0 polar granules) which are mathematical expressions of morphometric dependences of the structure of oocystic oocysts which are confirmed by the results of regression and correlation analysis. The dependence of the Y oocyte species on seven characteristics has been proved.

Conclusions. The morphological features that are mathematical expressions of morphometric dependences of the structure and identification of the species of turkey oocysts are determined with high accuracy. The relative error in determining the type of turkey eimerias does not exceed 2 %

Keywords: identification, eimeria oocysts, turkeys, morphometry, regression analysis, correlation

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1. Introduction

On the way to the industrialization of poultry farming, especially the breeding of turkeys Eimeriosis is a serious problem, could cause significant economic losses even in the subclinical course [1, 2]. In turkeys, eimeriosis is caused by seven types of pathogens *Eimeria meleagridis* (Tyzzer, 1929), *Eimeria dispersa* (Tyzzer, 1929), *Eimeria meleagrimitis* (Tyzzer, 1929) [3–6], *Eimeria gallopavonis* (Hawkins, 1952), *Eimeria adenoides* (Moore and Brown, 1952), *Eimeria innocua* (Moore and Brown, 1952), *Eimeria subrotunda* (Moore, Brown, Carter, 1954) [7–11], belonging to the subkingdom of Protozoa, belonging to the subkingdom Protozoa, super-type Alveolata (Cavalier-Smith, 1991), infratype Apicomplexa (Levin, 1970), class Sporozoa (Leuckart, 1879), subclass Coccidia (Leuckart, 1879), series Eucoccidiida, suborder Eimeriina, family Eimeriidae, subfam-

ily Eimeriinae, genus *Eimeria* [1, 11–14]. The causative agents of turkey eimeriosis were first discovered and described by T. Smith (1895) under the names *Coccidium oviforme* and *Coccidium tenellum*, which were similar and previously described in rabbits and chickens [9]. R. Hadlei (1911) isolated eimeria oocysts from turkey and described them as a species of *Eimeria avium*. W.T. Jhonson reported on the specificity of *Eimeria* species in turkeys (1923) [7, 8]. reported the presence of independently existing species of eimeria in turkeys, and *E. Tyzzer* described in detail the causative agents of eimeriosis of turkeys such as *E. meleagridis* (E. Tyzzer, 1929), *E. meleagridis* (E. Tyzzer, 1929) and *E. dispersa* (Tyzzer, 1929) [8–10].

Up to now, the identification of pathogens of eimeriosis of turkeys is carried out according to their original descriptions and data determinants [15], consid-

ering the localization in the intestine. oocyst morphology, biology, longitude of prepatent and patent periods, presence of cross-immunity. However, some of these parameters may coincide or be defined insufficiently, which complicates their identification.

Analyzing the data of the literature on the morphology and biology of turkey eimeria [13] it should be noted that during the research there were contradictory and ambiguous results, which did not correspond to the original descriptions of pathogens, which indicated imperfection and difficulty in determining species [5, 16] and required comparison of the obtained results with descriptive materials [3, 4, 8, 15] and the location of pathogens in the body of turkeys. The aim of our work is to establish the type of oocysts of eimeria of turkeys by morphometric parameters.

There are also pathomorphological methods for diagnosing eimeriosis, which consider the peculiarities of the endogenous cycle of pathogens, their location in the intestinal tract and the presence of characteristic pathological and histopathological changes [5, 16], taking into account the morphology of oocysts, longitude (terms) of prepatent and patent development. Significant progress in the identification of causative agents of turkey eimeriosis has been the development of real-time PCR methods [17, 18] and mitochondrial genome [18, 19]. However, to this day, the identification of oocysts by morphological characteristics remains relevant. There is a method of identifying Eimeric oocysts, which consists in measuring the smallest and largest radii of curvature of the poles of the oocyst contour, complex calculations of the species indicator by the value of which identify the type of Eimeris [20], but to measure the curvature of oocysts is extremely difficult.

Therefore, further research is needed to improve the identification of pathogens of eimeriosis by morphological indicators.

2. Materials and methods

The research was conducted in the scientific laboratories of the Department of Pharmacology and Parasitology State Biotechnological University, laboratory of Epizootology and Parasitology Odessa Research Center, National Scientific Center "Institute of Experimental and Clinical Veterinary Medicine" National Academy of Agrarian Sciences of Ukraine, laboratory of Department of Artificial Intelligence, Faculty of Computer Science, Kharkiv National V. N. Karazin University

Material for the research (faeces) was obtained from suspected and clinically ill Eimeriosis turkeys of specialized poultry farms of Kharkiv region.

The material for the study was Eimeria srp oocysts isolated by flotation from the faeces of turkeys with suspected or diagnosed eimeriosis [21].

Morphometry of Eimeria oocysts (n=255) (measurement of oocyst length and width) was performed on an Axioskop-40 microscope magnification ($\times 400$) using an eyepiece micrometer, pre-determining the value of its scale (division price) of the object with a micrometer. Then the photos of oocysts were processed using the Adobe Photoshop CS6 13.1.2 program. The linear size

of the oocyst was determined accurate to about 0.05 μm .

It has been defined eight explanatory factors to define species of pathogen:

X_1 – the length of the oocyst in μm ;

X_2 – the width of oocysts in μm ;

X_3 – area of oocysts in μm^2 ;

X_4 – eccentricity of the model ellipse, the major axis of which is the length of the oocyst, and the minor one – the width of the oocyst, eccentricity is determined

by the formula $X_4 = \sqrt{1 - \frac{X_2^2}{X_1^2}}$;

X_5 – the ratio of the width of the oocyst to its length $\left(X_5 = \frac{X_2}{X_1} \right)$;

X_6 – the largest curvature of the model ellipse at its pole on the major axis in μm^{-1} , which is determined by the formula: $X_6 = \frac{2X_1}{X_2^2}$;

X_7 – the smallest curvature of the model ellipse at its pole on the minor axis in μm^{-1} , which is determined by the formula: $X_7 = \frac{2X_1}{X_2^2}$;

X_8 – dichotomous feature which is defined as the presence (value 1) or absence (value 0) of the polar granule.

It was introduced dichotomous (boolean) variable Y to specify different species of turkeys' oocysts of Eimeria:

Y=1 (for the species E. innocua);

Y=2 (for the species E. meleagrimitis);

Y=3 (for the species E. meleagridis);

Y=4 (for the species E. gallopavonis);

Y=5 (for the species E. adenoides).

Ranking was performed by the values of length and area of oocysts from the smallest to the largest.

To process the results of research were used the methods of correlation and regression analysis, as well as analysis of variance (ANOVA) [22].

The multiple correlation analysis methods were used to define the species of oocysts of Eimeria Y by the parameters $X_1 - X_2$ using "Correlation" tool from "Data analysis" package in MS Excel program [23].

3. Results

According to the measured values of width and length of oocysts of Eimeria (Table 1) it was calculated the following parameters:

area of oocysts – X_3 ;

eccentricity – X_4 ;

the ratio of the oocyst's width to its length – X_5 ;

the largest and smallest curvature of the ellipse – X_6, X_7 ;

such morphological parameters as the presence (1) or absence (0) of polar granules – X_8 .

The following correlation matrix (Table 2) was build using the data from Table 1.

Table 1

The value of explanatory factors, M±m

Species of Eimeria	X1, μm	X2, μm	X3, μm ²	X4	X5	X6, μm ⁻¹	X7, μm ⁻¹	X8
E. gallopavonis (n=50)	24.37±0.09	16.11±0.07	308.5±2.1	0.750±0.002	0.661±0.002	0.188±0.001	0.054±0.000	0
E. meleagrimitis (n=50)	19.69±0.03	15.55±0.05	240.6±1.1	0.613±0.002	0.790±0.002	0.163±0.001	0.080±0.000	0
E. adenoides (n=51)	24.72±0.1	16.77±0.08	325.8±2.9	0.735±0.002	0.678±0.002	0.176±0.001	0.054±0.000	1
E. Meleagridis (n=53)	21.98±0.1	17.42±0.1	301.1±2.9	0.609±0.003	0.793±0.002	0.145±0.001	0.072±0.000	0
E. innocua (n=51)	16.10±0.01	15.33±0.04	193.9±0.5	0.301±0.006	0.952±0.002	0.137±0.001	0.118±0.000	0

Table 2

Correlation matrix for explanatory and explained parameters

Features	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	X6	X7	X8	Y
X1	1								
X2	0.6032	1							
X3	0.9675	0.7839	1						
X4	0.9299	0.3883	0.8416	1					
X5	-0.9453	-0.3319	-0.8374	-0.9822	1				
X6	0.7107	-0.1288	0.5104	0.8264	-0.8877	1			
X7	-0.9764	-0.5049	-0.9149	-0.9855	0.9791	-0.7780	1		
X8	0.4973	0.7681	0.6283	0.3509	-0.3013	-0.0611	-0.4321	1	
Y	0.9546	0.5217	0.9083	0.8704	-0.9086	0.7157	-0.9187	0.5734	1

It was indicated a strong correlation between the species of oocyst Y and its length X₁ (correlation coefficient 0.9546), the total area X₃ (0.9083) as well as a very strong negative correlation with the ratio of width to length X₅ (-0.9086) and the curvature of the ellipse X₇ (-0.9187). Due to a strong correlation with several parameters, a strong multicollinearity (linear connection)

takes place. This could possibly lead (and will lead, as will be proved below) to the situation when parameter X₁ is insignificant and could be ignored during analysis.

It was used ANOVA analysis to build an analytical relationship between the species of oocyst Y and all defined parameters X₁-X₇. The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3

Final statistics of ANOVA

RESULTS						
Regression statistics						
Multiple R	0.9916					
R-square	0.9832					
Adjusted R-square	0.9826					
Standard Error	0.1856					
Observations	255					
Analysis of variance						
	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F	
Regression	8	495.5088	61.9386	1797.753	1.8E-213	
Residual	246	8.4755	0.0345			
Total	254	503.9843				
	Coefficients	Standard Error	T Stat	P-value	Lower 95 %	Upper 95 %
Y	74.892	12.549	5.9675	8.35E-09	50.17269	99.6106
X1	0.287	0.314	0.9128	0.36223	-0.33185	0.90512
X2	5.527	1.491	3.7061	0.00026	2.589843	8.46516
X3	-0.134	0.032	-4.1909	3.88E-05	-0.19719	-0.0711
X4	-10.400	2.157	-4.8213	2.5E-06	-14.649	-6.1514
X5	-188.590	35.298	-5.3428	2.09E-07	-258.115	-119.06
X6	-111.140	14.254	-7.7973	1.79E-13	-139.215	-83.066
X7	513.305	110.953	4.6263	6.02E-06	294.7649	731.844
X8	0.887	0.041	21.5466	1.44E-58	0.806174	0.96839

It was established that parameter X_1 (the length of the oocyst) is insignificant according to Student (level of confidence, $p < 0.36$). Accordingly, parameter X_1 should be removed from the regression equation. However, this

does not mean that the parameter X_1 should not be measured at all due to this indicator is indirectly included in the parameter X_1-X_7 . There are the results of the final statistics in Table 4.

Table 4

Final depreciated statistics of ANOVA

RESULTS						
<i>Regression statistics</i>						
Multiple R	0.991527					
R-square	0.983126					
Adjusted R-square	0.982648					
Standard Error	0.185553					
Observations	255					
Analysis of variance						
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>	
Regression	7	495.4801	70.78287	2055.844	5.8338E-215	
Residual	247	8.504231	0.03443			
Total	254	503.9843				
	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Lower 95 %</i>	<i>Upper 95 %</i>
Y	83.463	8.323	10.02735	4.5E-20	67.0688	99.8571
X2	5.721	1.476	3.876758	0.000136	2.8145	8.6280
X3	-0.127	0.031	-4.09314	5.77E-05	-0.1881	-0.0659
X4	-11.929	1.358	-8.78226	2.73E-16	-14.6050	-9.2541
X5	-198.555	33.556	-5.91709	1.09E-08	-264.6483	-132.462
X6	-110.535	14.233	-7.76589	2.16E-13	-138.5690	-82.5005
X7	526.497	109.971	4.787599	2.91E-06	309.8964	743.0970
X8	0.886	0.041	21.53467	1.28E-58	0.8048	0.9668

The values in Table 4 demonstrates that the regression equation is reliably significant by the Fisher's criterion, all features and coefficients are significant by Student's criterion ($p < 0.0001$), the regression has high value of multiple correlation coefficient (0.9915) and a high value of the coefficient of determination normalized to the number of degrees of freedom (0.9826).

So, the dependence of the species of oocyst Y on the 7 factors identified above is qualitative and could be represented by the following formula:

$$Y = 83.463 + 5.721X_2 - 0.127X_3 - 11.929X_4 - 198.555X_5 - 110.535X_6 + 526.497X_7 + 0.886X_8.$$

The absolute error of the multiple linear regression model is represented as the deviation of the predicted indicator of the species of oocyst between Y_{pred} and the Y_{fact} . It was incorrectly identified only 5 of 255 oocyst samples, the relative error in determining the species of Eimeria of turkey < 2 %. Below are the actual values Y_{fact} , the predicted values Y_{pred} , and the absolute error of the species determination (Table 5). It was represented only five samples in the Table 5 due to the entire dataset is too huge.

Table 5

The results of incorrect determination of oocysts of Eimeria turkeys

No. sample.	Features										Absolute. Error
	$X_1, \mu m$	$X_2, \mu m$	$X_3, \mu m^2$	X_4	X_5	$X_6, \mu m^{-1}$	$X_7, \mu m^{-1}$	X_8	Y_{fact}	Y_{pred}	
20	23.82	17.60	329.25	0.674	0.739	0.154	0.062	0	4	3	1
129	24.25	17.40	331.39	0.697	0.718	0.160	0.059	1	5	4	1
156	23.20	17.90	326.15	0.636	0.772	0.145	0.067	1	3	4	1
159	23.25	17.80	325.03	0.643	0.766	0.147	0.066	1	3	4	1
175	22.45	15.95	281.23	0.704	0.710	0.176	0.063	1	3	4	1

4. Discussion

Summarizing the results of the research, it should be noted that the regression analysis of morphometric parameters of oocysts is a reliable way to determine the species affiliation of Eimeria pathogens. With our studies the previously proposed methods for the identification of pathogens of oocysts of Eimeria require significant efforts of the researcher to clarify the morphological and biological characteristics of the

pathogens and compare them with the descriptive data of identification tables.

The form index has only an ancillary value, as it does not have high specificity for all types of pathogens and does not provide a complete objective assessment [8, 13-15, 21]. The method of Eimeria species identification based on two-dimensional mathematical analysis using an identification index (the ratio of the square of the perimeter of the contour to the surface area of the oocyst [6, 20]

does not fully reflect the morphological features of oocysts as well as the usage of Lagrange interpolation polynomials takes a long time.

Whereas in our work the image obtained on a microscope of oocysts of eimeria is first subjected to morphometry to determine: X_1 – the length of the oocyst in μm ; X_2 – oocyst width in μm and calculate other indicators (X_3 – X_7); X_8 – the presence (value 1) or absence (value 0) of the polar bead and automatically using the tool “Regression” from the package “Data Analysis” MS Excel perform analysis and construct multiple linear regression equations to determine the species of oocyst Y. Thus, according to the results of mathematical processing of morphometric dependences of the oocyst structure using the tool “Correlation”, a strong correlation was found between the type of oocyst and its length (correlation coefficient 0.9546), area (0.9083) and a strong negative correlation between length to width (–0.9086) and curvature of the ellipse (–0.9187).

5. Conclusions

1. It was determined morphological features that are mathematical expressions of morphometric dependences of the structure and identification of the species of oocysts of turkeys.

2. The use of correlation and regression analysis, as well as analysis of variance (ANOVA) allows to reliably identify 98 % of the species affiliation of oocysts of Eimeric turkeys.

Conflict of interests

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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References

1. Boenigk, J., Ereshefsky, M., Hoef-Emden, K., Mallet, J., Bass, D. (2012). Concepts in protistology: Species definitions and boundaries. *European Journal of Protistology*, 48 (2), 96–102. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejop.2011.11.004>
2. Gussem, M. (2007). Coccidiosis in poultry: review on diagnosis, control, prevention and interaction with overall gut health, 16-th European Symposium on Poultry Nutrition. Strasbourg, 26–30.
3. Long, P. L., Millard, B. J. (1979). Studies on *Eimeria dispersa* Tyzzer 1929 in turkeys. *Parasitology*, 78 (1), 41–51. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1017/s0031182000048575>
4. Matsler, P. L., Chapman, H. D. (2006). Characterization of a Strain of *Eimeria meleagridis* from the Turkey. *Avian Diseases*, 50 (4), 599–604. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1637/7646-051006r.1>
5. Matsler, P. L., Chapman, H. D. (2007). Selection for early (precocious) development of *Eimeria meleagridis* in the turkey. *Avian Diseases*, 51, 122–124. doi: [http://doi.org/10.1637/0005-2086\(2007\)051\[0122:sfepdo\]2.0.co;2](http://doi.org/10.1637/0005-2086(2007)051[0122:sfepdo]2.0.co;2)
6. Mironenko, V. M. (2009). Identification of the type of eimeria based on two-dimensional mathematical analysis of the structure of oocysts. Scientific notes of the educational institution “Vitebsk Order” Sign of Honor “State Academy of Veterinary Medicine”, 45 (2 (1)), 123–126. Available at: <https://repo.vsavm.by/handle/123456789/6770>
7. Hawkins, P. A. (1950). Coccidiosis of the Turkey. *Journal of Parasitology*, 36, 42–43.
8. Poplstein, M., Vrba, V. (2011). Description of the two strains of turkey coccidia *Eimeria adenoeides* with remarkable morphological variability. *Parasitology*, 138 (10), 1211–1216. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1017/s0031182011001090>
9. Vrba, V., Pakandl, M. (2014). Coccidia of turkey: from isolation, characterisation and comparison to molecular phylogeny and molecular diagnostics. *International Journal for Parasitology*, 44 (13), 985–1000. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpara.2014.06.004>
10. Williams, R. B. (2010). The correct date of the original description and availability of the coccidian name *Eimeria meleagridis* Tyzzer (Apicomplexa: Eimeriorina: Eimeriidae). *Systematic Parasitology*, 76 (1), 77–79. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s11230-010-9236-0>
11. Chapman, H. D. (2003). Origins of coccidiosis research in the fowl*the first fifty years. *Avian Diseases*, 47 (1), 1–20. doi: [http://doi.org/10.1637/0005-2086\(2003\)047\[0001:ooocrit\]2.0.co;2](http://doi.org/10.1637/0005-2086(2003)047[0001:ooocrit]2.0.co;2)
12. Cavalier-Smith, T. (2003). Protist phylogeny and the high-level classification of Protozoa. *European Journal of Protistology*, 39 (4), 338–348. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1078/0932-4739-00002>
13. Chapman, H. D. (2008). Coccidiosis in the turkey. *Avian Pathology*, 37 (3), 205–223. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1080/03079450802050689>
14. Pellerdy, L. P. (1974). *Coccidia and coccidiosis*. Berlin: Verlag Paul Parey and Akademiai Kiado, 959.
15. Gadelhaq, S. M., Habelaty, A. (2019). The occurrence and distribution pattern of *Eimeria* species among domestic pigeons in Minia, Egypt. *Journal of Veterinary Medical Research*, 26 (2), 164–173. doi: <http://doi.org/10.21608/jvmr.2019.66098>
16. Ogedengbe, M. E., El-Sherry, S., Whale, J., Barta, J. R. (2014). Complete mitochondrial genome sequences from five *Eimeria* species (Apicomplexa; Coccidia; Eimeriidae) infecting domestic turkeys. *Parasites & Vectors*, 7 (1). doi: <http://doi.org/10.1186/1756-3305-7-335>
17. El-Sherry, S., Ogedengbe, M. E., Hafeez, M. A., Sayf-Al-Din, M., Gad, N., Barta, J. R. (2018). Cecal coccidiosis in turkeys: Comparative biology of *Eimeria* species in the lower intestinal tract of turkeys using genetically typed, single oocyst-derived lines. *Parasitology Research*, 118 (2), 583–598. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00436-018-6147-5>
18. Chapman, H. D. (2014). Milestones in avian coccidiosis research: A review. *Poultry Science*, 93 (3), 501–511. doi: <http://doi.org/10.3382/ps.2013-03634>
19. Hafeez, M. A., Shivaramaiah, S., Dorsey, K. M., Ogedengbe, M. E., El-Sherry, S., Whale, J. et. al. (2015). Simultaneous identification and DNA barcoding of six *Eimeria* species infecting turkeys using PCR primers targeting the mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (mtCOI) locus. *Parasitology Research*, 114 (5), 1761–1768. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00436-015-4361-y>
20. Mironenko, V. M., Korchevskaia, H. A. (2014). IT-Identification of disease agents of parasitoses, Parasitoses of animals in the National Park “Pripiatskii” and fight measures against them with usage of IT technologies. *Vitebsk*, 22–26.

21. Long, P. L., Millard, B. J. (1979). Coccidiosis in turkeys: some recent work in Britain. *Turkeys*, 19–21.
22. Gmurman, V. Ye. (2008). *Theory of Probability and Mathematical Statistics*. Moscow Vischaya shkola, 400.
23. Lebedko, E. Ya., Khokhlov, A. M., Baranovskiy, D. I., Getmanets, O. M. (2018). *Biometrics in MS Excel*. Moscow, Saint Petersburg: Lan, 172.

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